

NUMETRICAL STUDY ON CARBON FIBRE PULLOUT USING A COHESIVE ZONE MODEL

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Keywords: *carbon fibre, pullout, cohesive zone model*

1 Introduction

Carbon fibre used in advanced composites contains at least 92% carbon [1]. The diameter of carbon fibres is typically no larger than 10 μ m and its tensile strength can be up to 6GPa [2]. This type of material has generated a great scientific and industrial interest due to its remarkable characteristics and properties, such as structural perfection, small size, low density, high stiffness, low thermal expansion and high strength. Carbon fibres are currently used in conventional and novel areas, including aerospace, civil, electronic and medical engineering.

To achieve better mechanical properties such as higher strength, longer fatigue life, better wear resistance, carbon fibre can be wound or moulded with a lightweight matrix, such as epoxy. The interface between the fibre and the matrix often influences significantly the composite performance in all types of composites. The interfacial properties also play an important role in the failure mechanism and the fracture toughness of composites. Interface debonding is an important mechanism of energy absorption during the failure of a composite interface [3]. Intensive work has been done to understand the influence of interface on mechanical behaviour of composites and several techniques have been developed in analysing interfacial shear stress directly [3-5]. The single fibre pullout test is one of the most widely used techniques to quantify the interface strength. The condition of pullout test is that the length of fibre embedded in the matrix must be less than the critical embedded length for debonding. Otherwise the fibre will break before the debonding occurs. There are three stages during a single carbon fibre pullout, which include elastic deformation stage before debonding, debonding

stage and sliding stage. In the first stage, carbon fibre and the matrix are well bonded. As the pullout force increases, a crack propagates along the interface between the fibre and the matrix, leading to a complete debonding, which is the debonding stage. In the last stage, the carbon fibre is pulled out from the matrix, with friction acting between the two newly formed surfaces. Several analytical and numerical models have been developed for the single fibre pullout test. A shear lag model has been adopted by many researchers to investigate the stress distribution, interfacial debonding and frictional sliding process [5-7].

Cohesive zone (CZ) modelling [8] is a commonly used technique for investigating the fracture failure governed by crack or debonding propagation. It bridges the gap between the stress- and energy-based approaches. The concept of CZ modelling was originally proposed by Barenblatt [9] and Dugdale [10]. CZ modelling has been extensively used to simulate composite fracture under static, dynamic, and cyclic loading conditions [11]. Many studies have been carried out on the interfacial behaviours of Fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) and concrete under mode II conditions [12,13]. Harper and Hallett [14] applied CZ modelling to investigate the delamination in a double cantilever beam, in a three-point end-notched-flexure beam under Mode I, II and mixed-mode loading conditions. However, relatively little attention has been paid to use CZ modelling to numerically simulate the fibre pullout test. Tsai et al. [15] successfully used a mixed cohesive zone/friction interface model to simulate the copper fibre pullout by FEA.

The purpose of the present study is to investigate a single carbon fibre pullout test by using cohesive

zone modelling. In this paper, a numerical model is firstly established, followed by validation of the model by comparing with the experiment results. Finally, a parametric study was carried out to examine the effects of relevant parameters on the fibre pullout behaviour.

2 Numerical Model and Validation

2.1 Problem Definition

To simulate the process of a typical fibre pullout test, a concentric cylinder geometry model is developed, as shown in Fig 1. A carbon fibre with a radius R_f is embedded at the centre of the concentric cylinder of the matrix. L_e is the total embedded fibre length. The matrix is treated as a semi-infinite body, and therefore, the radius and depth of the matrix are much larger than the dimensions of the fibre in this numerical model. In the fibre pullout test, a pullout force is applied uniformly on the top surface of fibre in the axial direction. In this investigation, the dynamic effect is neglected, which corresponds to the cases with a low pullout rate. The debonding is assumed to initiate at the fibre-matrix interface and propagates longitudinally along the carbon fibre with increasing applied force.

2.2 Cohesive Zone Law

Cohesive zone model establishes the traction-separation relation for the interface. The traction across the interface increases and reaches to a peak value, then decreases and eventually vanishes, permitting a complete decohesion [16]. In this paper, a bilinear cohesive law is implemented which reduces the artificial compliance inherent in the intrinsic CZ model [17] (Fig. 2). The tangential relative displacement across the interface is denoted as δ . The mode II cohesive law can be represented as,

$$\tau_{is} = K\delta \quad 0 \leq \delta \leq \delta_s \quad (1)$$

where τ_{is} is average interfacial shear stress, K is the slop of the first portion of the curve ($K = \tau_{\max}/\delta_d$). τ_{\max} is the interfacial crack initiation stress under shear loading condition. δ_d and δ_s are respectively the initiate crack separation displacement, where

crack surfaces start to separate at the peak shear stress, and complete separation displacement, where the crack surfaces separate completely [18].

2.3 Single Fibre Pullout Simulation and Validation

The commercial finite element package Abaqus is used to perform the pullout simulation. Due to the symmetry of this problem, a 2D axisymmetric model is constructed, where a carbon fibre of $7\mu\text{m}$ diameter is embedded in a semi-infinite epoxy matrix (Fig. 3). The bottom of the model is therefore constrained in both the radial and axial directions. The vertical side along the axisymmetric axis is constrained only in the radial direction. The material properties are given in Table 1. A very fine mesh with the smallest elements of $1\mu\text{m} \times 1\mu\text{m}$ is used in the interface zone to ensure the accuracy of the numerical results. The maximum stress criterion for crack initiation is adopted in the CZ simulation. Three characteristic parameters of the interface are used to define the bilinear shaped CZ modelling, the interfacial crack initiation shear stress τ_{\max} , fracture energy G , and stiffness K [16]. The fracture energy of the interface for mode II is

$$G = \frac{1}{2} \tau_{\max} \delta_s \quad (2)$$

This fracture energy can be estimated based on the area under the force-displacement curves obtained from the experiment [14-16].

Based on the experiment results from Bogoeva-Gaceva et al. [19], the values of the three interfacial parameters are calibrated here through curve fitting. There are $\tau_{\max} = 45\text{MPa}$, $G = 562.5\text{J/m}^2$ and $K = 1.987\text{N/m}^3$. Fig. 4 shows that the simulated pullout curve from the fitted parameters agrees overall very well with the experimental curve by Bogoeva-Gaceva et al. [19], although the debonding force is slightly lower than the experimental value (0.096N versus 0.1N). This comparison indicates that cohesive zone model can be applied to numerically study carbon fibre pullout. The developed cohesive zone model is used to investigate the effects of relevant parameters on the fibre pullout behaviour in the following section.

3 Parametrical Study

3.1 Parametrical Analysis

The maximum pullout force (F_{\max}), the so called debonding force, is the most important parameter during a pullout test, which is used to calculate the average interfacial strength. Generally, the debonding force (F_{\max}) is a function of the parameters,

$$F_{\max} = f(\tau_{\max}, \delta_d, \delta_s, R_f, L_e, E_f, E_m, \nu_f, \nu_m, \mu) \quad (3)$$

where E_f and E_m are the Young's modulus of fibre and matrix. The parameters, ν_f and ν_m (elastic Poisson's ratio) and μ (frictional coefficient) are dimensionless.

Finite element (FE) simulations are carried out to numerically investigate the functional dependency of the listed parameters in (3) on the debonding force. The elastic Poisson's ratios, ν_f and ν_m , are kept respectively constant as 0.28 and 0.3 in all of following simulations. The debonding force, F_{\max} , is examined as each parameter, except ν_f and ν_m , varies individually in the FE simulation, whilst all other parameters are kept constant at their nominal values. The reasonable domains for each of the parameters are chosen based on the real fibre pullout test as shown in Table 2.

3.2 Parametrical Study

The influences of each parameter on the debonding force F_{\max} are discussed in this section.

3.2.1 Effect of the interfacial crack initiation shear stress τ_{\max}

Fig. 5 (a-d) shows the relationship between the debonding force and the interfacial crack initiation shear stress. It is clearly indicated that the debonding force increases with the value of the interfacial crack initiation shear stress almost linearly in all the cases. The numerical results show that the debonding force is almost proportional to the interfacial crack initiation shear stress.

Fig. 5(a) indicates that the debonding force can be influenced by the initiate crack separation

displacement δ_d . A lower pullout force is required for a higher value of initiate crack separation displacement δ_d . Fig. 5(b) shows that the influence of fibre complete separation displacement δ_s is fairly small. The maximum variation of F_{\max} is less than 2%. In Fig. 5(c), it can be seen that the influence of fibre radius R_f is significant. The debonding force increases as the fibre radius is increased. Fig. 5(d) shows that influence on the debonding force is more significant in higher embedded length ($L_e = 150\mu\text{m}$) than that in lower embedded length ($L_e = 50\mu\text{m}$). Furthermore, the linear relationship between the debonding force and the interfacial crack initiation shear stress is also observed for different Young's modulus of fibre (E_f) and matrix (E_m). The influence of Young's modulus is almost negligible. The change from the nominal value of F_{\max} is less than $\pm 2\%$. The influence of frictional coefficient on the debonding force is also negligible. This is because the friction only affects the pullout process after full debonding.

3.2.2 Effect of initiate crack separation displacement δ_d

The influence of the initiate crack separation displacement δ_d on the debonding force is further examined in Fig. 6. It shows again that the debonding force decreases slightly with the increase initiate crack separation displacement. According to the relation of $K = \tau_{\max} / \delta_d$, a higher initiate crack separation displacement results in a lower stiffness. In this simulation, it can be said that the stiffness might have a slight influence on the debonding force.

3.2.3 Effect of fibre geometric parameters, fibre radius R_f and embedded length L_e

The fibre geometric parameters are the fibre radius and its embedded length. The effect of the fibre radius on the debonding force is shown in Fig. 7(a). It can be observed that the debonding force F_{\max} increases linearly with fibre radius at any interfacial crack initiation shear stress. Fig. 7 (b) shows the relationship between the debonding force and the fibre embedded length. It clearly indicates that the

debonding force also increases linearly with the normalized embedded length L_e . These results indicated that the debonding force can be increased by increasing the fibre geometry.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, the single carbon fibre pullout test is studied by using the cohesive zone modelling. The finite element method is applied to systematically investigate the influence of different parameters involved in the fibre pullout test, which includes the interfacial crack initiation shear stress, fibre initiate crack separation displacement, fibre complete separation displacement, fibre radius, embedded length, Young's modulus and frictional coefficient. The results show that the debonding force has a linear relationship with the interfacial crack initiation shear stress and fibre geometric parameters. The debonding force slight decreases with increase of the fibre initiate crack separation displacement. Furthermore, the results show that the influences of Young's modulus, fibre complete separation displacement and frictional coefficient are negligible small. In the future work, the study will focus on the effect of thermal residual stress which is an additional tensile or compressive stress in both the fibre and matrix. The thermal residual stress is caused by the mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion during the curing process.

Fig.1. A schematic diagram of the fibre pullout model.

Fig. 2 Interfacial cohesive law.

Fig. 3 Axisymmetric finite element model for a single carbon fibre pullout: fine mesh in contact.

Fig. 4 Force-displacement curves for carbon fibre pullout test.

Fig. 5 (a-d) Influence of interfacial crack initiation shear stress on the debonding force for different cases.

Fig. 6 Influence of the initiate crack separation displacement on the debonding force.

Fig. 7 Influence of the fibre geometric parameters on the debonding force (a) fibre diameter R_f (b) fibre embedded length L_e .

Table 1 Material properties of fibre and matrix

Mechanical properties	Carbon fibre	Epoxy matrix
Young's Modulus (GPa)	238	3.4
Poisson's ratio	0.28	0.2

Table 2 Nominal, minimum and maximum values for investigated parameters

Parameter		Nominal	Min	Max
Interfacial crack initiation shear stress (MPa)	τ_{\max}	30	15	45
Initiate crack separation displacement (μm)	δ_d	20	15	24
Complete separation displacement (μm)	δ_s	25	21	30
Fibre radius (μm)	R_f	3.5	2	7
Embedded length (μm)	L_e	100	50	150
Fibre Young's modulus (GPa)	E_f	238	180	300
Matrix Young's modulus (GPa)	E_m	3.4	2	10
Frictional coefficient	μ	0.2	0.15	0.25

References

- [1] E. Fitzer "Carbon fibres filaments and composites". Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht, pp 3-41, 1990.
- [2] P. Morgan "Carbon fibers and their composites". CRC Press, pp 791-859, 2005.
- [3] X. Zhang, H.-Y. Liu, Y. Mai and X. Diao "On steady-state fibre pull-out I The stress field". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 59, pp 2179-2189, 1999.
- [4] H.-Y. Liu, L.-M. Zhou and Y.-W. Mai "Effect of interface roughness on fiber push-out stress". *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 78, No. 3, pp 560-566, 1995.
- [5] C. Hsueh "Interfacial debonding and fibre pull-out stresses of fibre-reinforced composites". *Materials Science and Engineering*, A123, pp 1-11, 1990.
- [6] L. Zhou, J. Kim and Y. Mai "On the single fibre pull-out problem: effect of loading method". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 45, No. 2, pp 153-160, 1992.
- [7] X. Chen, I. J. Beyerlein and L. C. Brinson "Curved-fibre pull-out model for nanocomposites. Part 1: Bonded stage formulation". *Mechanics of Materials*, Vol. 41, pp 279-292, 2009.
- [8] T. L. Anderson "Fracture mechanics". 3rd edition, Taylor and Francis, 2005.
- [9] G. I. Barenblatt "The formation of equilibrium cracks during brittle fracture. General ideas and hypothesis. axisymmetrical cracks". *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics*, Vol. 23, pp 434-444, 1959.
- [10] D. S. Dugdale "Yielding of steel sheets containing slits". *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, Vol. 8, pp 100-104, 1960.
- [11] L. D. Lorenzis and G. Zavarise "Cohesive zone modeling of interfacial stresses in plated beams". *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 46, pp 4181-4191, 2009.
- [12] B. Taljsten "Strengthening of concrete prism using the plate-bonding technique". *International Journal of Fracture*, Vol. 82, No. 3, pp 253-266, 1996.
- [13] J. G. Teng, H. Yuan and J. F. Chen "FRP-to-concrete interfaces between two adjacent cracks: theoretical model for debonding failure". *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 43, No. 18-19, pp 5750-5778, 2006.
- [14] P. W. Harper and S. R. Hallett "Cohesive zone length in numerical simulations of composite delamination". *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 75, pp 4774-4792, 2008.
- [15] J. H. Tsai, A. Patra and R. Wetherhold "Finite element simulation of shaped ductile fibre pullout using a mixed cohesive zone/friction interface model". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 36, pp 827-838, 2005.
- [16] N. Chandra, H. Li, C. Shet and H. Ghonem "Some issues in the application of cohesive zone models for metal-ceramic interfaces". *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 39, pp 2827-55, 2002.
- [17] S. H. Song, G. H. Paulino and W. G. Buttlar "A bilinear cohesive zone model tailored for fracture of asphalt concrete considering viscoelastic bulk material". *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 73, No. 18, pp 2829-2848, 2006.
- [18] SIMULA "ABAQUS 6.9 Documentation". Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., 2009
- [19] G. Bogoeva-Gaceva, and E. Miider, L. Hiublner and K. Sahre "Parameters affecting the interface properties in carbon fibre/epoxy systems". *Composites*, Vol. 26, pp 103-107, 1995.